

Tomato Fruit Color Changes during Ripening of Vine

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Abstract : Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) hybrid 'Brooklyn' was investigated at the LRCAF Institute of Horticulture. For investigation, five green tomatoes, which were grown on vine, were selected. Color measurements were made in the greenhouse with the same selected tomato fruits (fruits were not harvested and were growing and ripening on tomato vine through all experiment) in every two days while tomatoes fruits became fully ripen. Study showed that color index L has tendency to decline and established determination coefficient (R²) was 0.9504. Also, hue angle has tendency to decline during tomato fruit ripening on vine and it's coefficient of determination (R²) reached-0.9739. Opposite tendency was determined with color index a, which has tendency to increase during tomato ripening and that was expressed by polynomial trendline where coefficient of determination (R²) reached-0.9592.

Keywords : color, color index, ripening, tomato

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